

LandSense

A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace
for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring

Deliverable 6.2

Dissemination Tools and Communication Strategies I

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Short Description:
The LandSense Dissemination Tools and Communication Strategy I document provides guidance and direction for all LandSense communication activities with external actors. It ensures a unified approach across the entire LandSense consortium, covering WP6 activities and has a strong link to the future exploitation strategy and to the communication within the different LandSense Campaigns. It explains the available LandSense communication tools in detail and provides measures to evaluate and monitor the impact.
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List of Acronyms

CO	Citizen Observatory
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EC	European Commission
EO	Earth Observation
LEP	LandSense Engagement Platform
LULC	Land Use Land Cover
NGO	Non-governmental organisations
SME	Small and medium size enterprise

1 Introduction

LandSense is building an innovative Citizen Observatory (CO) in the field of Land Use Land Cover (LULC), which collects data both actively (through citizens) and passively (from authoritative, and open access sources) and integrates them to provide valuable quality-assured in-situ data for small and medium size enterprises (SMEs), larger businesses, government agencies, Non-governmental organisations (NGO) and researchers.

Citizen Observatories are community-based environmental monitoring and information systems. They build on innovative and novel Earth Observation (EO) mobile applications, allowing end-users, i.e. citizens to not only play a key role in LULC monitoring, but also to be directly involved in the development of such applications. As such, the participation of citizens represents a vital part in the LandSense campaigns.

The EO data economy is moving towards becoming a highly competitive market segment. Solution providers are reliant on high quality data as they need to deliver contextually appropriate EO-based value-added products and services. In-situ data plays a crucial role in ensuring that EO data are properly calibrated and validated and enables EO companies to significantly increase the quality of their products and services.

To increase the awareness and the participatory engagement of key stakeholders like citizens, dissemination and communication activities play a vital role throughout the project. Being a continuous process, the LandSense communication strategy aims at transmitting the added value of the project and to ensure the visibility of project results and their take-up by decision-makers beyond the lifetime of the project. A variety of communication tools are available to guarantee that information is shared with appropriate audiences on a timely basis (see Section 4). Additionally, to help improve the coordination between existing COs and related citizen science activities, WeObserve, a Horizon 2020 Coordination and Support Action (CSA) has been recently launched. The WeObserve consortium is also led by the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA). As such, there will be strong collaboration between the projects and the LandSense Dissemination and Communication Strategy will be linked to WeObserve outreach to amplify its impact.

The following document represents a framework for the envisaged communication activities to be realized during the lifetime of the LandSense project, guided by the overall project objectives (Section 2) along with the aim of achieving the long- term impact of the project results.

In order to maximize the efforts and to obtain the best results, the LandSense communication and dissemination plan should be seen as a living document. That is, the communication strategy is constantly revised and extended in accordance with the information received from the work packages and with new dissemination opportunities that may arise during the project life time. Dissemination and communication actions will be periodically re-evaluated and realigned based on the analysis of metrics to try to improve the impact of these actions.

2 Dissemination and communication objectives

The LandSense communication and dissemination strategy is about increasing the visibility of the LandSense project activities and results by raising awareness in the community of important stakeholders including researchers, public authorities, citizens as well as professionals. The objectives of the LandSense dissemination and communication strategy include:

✓ **Build awareness**

Distribution of LandSense progress, deliverables, events, outcomes, factsheets and services via open, and transparent channels (i.e. the LandSense Engagement Platform, social media channels, existing partner networks, etc.). The project will emphasize the LandSense Engagement Platform (LEP) as the key dissemination and communication vehicle for the project, which will function as a single point of access via www.landsense.eu. Furthermore, the consortium will actively engage the existing networks and communication channels of the partners to widely promote and gain high visibility for the project work and outcomes on a European as well as international level.

✓ **Foster participation**

Mobilize and stimulate the active participation of citizens within LandSense campaigns for in-situ data acquisition and participatory LULC monitoring within Europe and internationally. In particular, facilitate the use of the LEP as a key component of the LandSense Citizen Observatory.

✓ **Trigger change**

Promote the development of an innovative citizen observatory for LULC monitoring, which collects data actively through citizens and passively from other sources and integrates them into an open platform.

✓ **Stimulate service uptake**

Target the right audience from the public and private sector to stimulate the uptake of LandSense services via the Services Incubator at strategic times along the project lifetime. Key activities will help to build an ecosystem of actors that promotes the extension of European markets and opportunities in the field of in-situ monitoring.

3 LandSense communication audience

3.1 General audience

The LandSense communication audience is very diverse and the LandSense communication strategy targets a multidisciplinary stakeholder group coming from science, technology, business and policy domains as well as European networks and NGOs.

The transfer of project outputs to **public authorities and European policy makers** is crucial for guaranteeing the impact of the LandSense project. Hence LandSense is reaching out to institutions and organisations at a local, regional, national and European level. In particular, LandSense results will be shared with decision-makers; specific and targeted communication activities for local policy makers are intended to contribute to the take up of lessons learned and the results arising from the different LandSense campaigns.

The **general public** represents a key target audience as citizens will be actively involved in the various LandSense campaigns. In particular, LandSense targets citizens that are already interested in LandSense relevant topics such as urban landscape dynamics, agricultural land use as well as forest and habitat monitoring, in particular, and land use and land cover issues in general.

LandSense will foster innovative citizen science driven services. **Businesses**, offering innovative technological solutions, might be highly interested in knowing more about the impact of the LandSense campaigns and how existing tools and services can be deployed to offer commercial services. Thus, LandSense communication activities will also take businesses into consideration, by producing materials with a non-specialist, less technological, easily accessible and understandable language.

LandSense will produce cutting-edge results in the LULC domain, making **researchers and scientists** a top target audience. To reach this target group, planned activities include:

- Peer-reviewed articles and other scientific publications
- Presentations at major national and international conferences
- External seminars and workshops
- LandSense workshops and the LandSense Innovation Challenge (WP6)
- Linking LandSense research with other research projects and other established Citizen Observatories (e.g. SCENT, GroundTruth 2.0, GROW, see Section 4.4)

Existing **European networks** as well as **NGOs** are crucial for further distributing LandSense activities and outputs. In particular, it is envisaged to use existing networks, taking advantage of the multiplier effect. Promotional materials will be designed so that non-experts with no technical background can easily access and understand the LandSense concepts and campaigns. Furthermore, the content will be translated into different languages depending upon the location.

A detailed overview of the respective target group objectives and the content to be communicated is provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Target groups of LandSense communication strategy, objectives and content

Target group	Objective	Content
Public authorities: <i>Policy and decision makers</i> <i>Open data specialists</i> <i>Staff with specialist technical knowledge in technical departments or consultants</i>	1) Raising awareness of LandSense and the benefits of involving citizens in the planning process through LEP 2) Promoting the collection of high-quality open data which can be fed into the LandSense Citizen Observatory	Reports, deliverables, project results
EU policy makers	1) Sensitizing them to the possibilities of bringing citizens into the planning process via smart means of using open data	Reports, deliverables, project results
General public: <i>Citizens with a strong interest in land use and land cover data</i>	1) Raise awareness and encourage active participation in the LandSense Campaigns and engagement with LEP	General information in the project, Project campaigns, Events, Information days
Business: <i>Multinational companies</i> <i>SMEs,</i> <i>Start-ups in different fields</i>	1) Make them aware of the potential of LandSense and the chance to use open data and the LEP to bolster their business	Science-related information, Events (innovation workshops, citizen science conferences), information days, training workshops
Researchers: Universities Research & technology organisations Corporate researchers	1) Make them aware of the potential of LandSense and the chance to use open data and the LEP for their research	Science-related information, Events (academic workshops, bilateral dissemination events), information days, training workshops
European Networks & NGOs	1) Raising awareness of LandSense and tapping into the multiplier effect through their networks	General information on the project, Project campaigns, Events, Information days

3.2 LandSense Campaign specific target groups

Apart from the general audience, the LandSense communication strategy is also targeting specific target groups related to the LandSense Campaigns as identified by the campaign leaders during the user requirements workshop (

Table 2). Any communication will be tailored towards the technical and scientific understanding of these target groups in order to achieve the highest possible impact.

Table 2: LandSense Campaign specific target groups

LandSense Campaign	Main campaign goal	Target groups
LULC French Campaign in Occitanie Region	Experimentation with land monitoring by engaging with citizens and local authorities, decision support, local planning	Local authorities Students OSM community Citizens Research community
FREI.RAUM.NETZ App	Empower citizens to create emotional maps in the city, to track activities of people in green open spaces and to empower them to express their interests in further activities	Students Experts Citizens
Land use validation and machine training	Validation of the OSMLanduse product and collection of data for further improvement.	Researcher & students Decision makers Engaged Citizens/ OSM community
Crowdsourcing perceived qualities of urban green spaces	Support policy makers with location specific data on quality of green spaces and test the usefulness of a smartphone app for crowdsourcing policy relevant information on the quality of green spaces	Department of Planning and Sustainability – Municipality of Amsterdam Residents of Amsterdam Students
Build, Measure, Learn! A New Take on Citizen Science for agricultural monitoring	This pilot will demonstrate the benefits that citizen science can bring to the farmer and scientific community.	High school students Farmers
Report it! Join us and report threats to biodiversity and habitat changes in your area!	Establishment of a combined habitat change alert system that uses remote sensing and in-situ validation from volunteers to improve and update existing information on bird habitats and to make it available to site managers and decision-making authorities.	Local conservation groups National IBA coordinators IBA caretakers Citizen bird watchers Other citizens: Nature lovers, outdoor sport people, biology students, non-bird naturalists

4 Communication Tools

The LandSense communication and dissemination team will use a wide variety of **online tools, offline materials, articles, reports, presentations, networking, meetings and events** as well as **press releases and other media channels** in order to reach the general audience as well as specific target audiences identified in Section 3. To attract a large audience and reach a high number of persons within all target groups, the project will not only create some specific communication material, but it will also actively participate in and use existing channels and networks of the LandSense consortium partners (e.g. Global2000, BirdLife International, University of Heidelberg). These networks are described in detail in D6.1. DEC Strategy, Operative Plan and SOPs.

4.1 Online tools

4.1.1 LandSense Website

At present, the main LandSense dissemination channel is its official website (<https://landsense.eu/>), which hosts a description of the project, the consortium, the LandSense themes as well as the recently launched LandSense Innovation Challenge. The website is also linked to a Newsletter engine (MailChimp) as a way of collecting names and email addresses of people interested in LandSense. Finally, a section is dedicated to the project's updates (News) and the website is linked to existing social media platforms by hosting a Twitter and Facebook widget in the home page.

The website is designed to guarantee a high level of accessibility and usability. To increase the impact of the project, the information materials use illustrative visual aids such as charts and infographics. Further, the information on the LandSense website is kept scientific and accurate, to allow the reader to gain good general insights into the project's goals and methodology. However, we are avoiding overly technical jargon in order to allow people from outside the scientific research field to easily understand the information provided.

Connecting citizens with satellite imagery to transform
environmental decision making

Figure 1: LandSense Webpage – Welcome screen

With the launch of the LEP (Section 4.1.2) planned for March 2018, the content of the LandSense website will be moved to the LEP in a step-by-step process and the LEP will be the key dissemination and communication vehicle for the project, functioning as a single point of access via www.landsense.eu.

4.1.2 LandSense Engagement Platform (LEP)

An important part of the LandSense Citizen Observatory is the LandSense Engagement Platform, a service platform comprised of highly marketable EO-based solutions that contribute to the transfer, assessment, valuation, uptake and exploitation of LULC data and related results. The platform will offer collaborative mapping functionalities to allow citizens to view, analyze and share data collected from different campaigns and create their own maps, individually and collaboratively. In addition, citizens can participate in ongoing LandSense demonstration cases using their own devices (e.g. mobile phones and tablets), through interactive reporting and gaming applications, as well as launching their own campaigns. This interaction is achieved by bringing together and extending various key pieces of technology like: Geo-Wiki, LACO-Wiki, Geopedia, Sentinel Hub and the Earth Observation Data Centre.

In the long term, all components of the LandSense website will be moved to the LEP, which will act as the key dissemination and communication vehicle for the project, functioning as a single point of access via www.landsense.eu.

At this point in time, a beta version of the LEP is already in place that showcases each of the LandSense Campaigns and which will be launched by the end of February 2018.

4.1.3 Social Media

At present, LandSense has set up two active accounts in the most used social media platforms - Twitter and Facebook - to disseminate its activities, upcoming and past events as well as results, and in general to share experiences, and to initiate and participate in conversations about the project:

- Twitter: @LandSense (<https://twitter.com/landsense>)
- Facebook page (<https://www.facebook.com/LandSense.eu/>)

At present, LandSense has a total of 648 followers on Twitter and 203 on Facebook, respectively.

4.1.4 LandSense e-Newsletter

Since September 2017, LandSense has published a newsletter approximately every 3 months, depending on the availability of new and relevant information. The objective of the newsletter is to present information about the project's activities and outcomes and to proactively initiate conversations with stakeholders about ongoing research themes. Upcoming events are communicated also communicated via the newsletter.

A mailing list was created, including all the persons interested in the newsletter. A section is inserted in the project website in which people can subscribe to the newsletter (see [here](#)). Subscription is also possible during project events as well as through direct contact with LandSense partners. To facilitate the management of the mailing list and the distribution of the newsletter, the LandSense dissemination and communication team has set up MailChimp.

At present the LandSense e-Newsletter has a total of 198 subscribers and the statistics for the latest newsletters are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: LandSense e-Newsletter statistics (September 2017 to February 2018)

Newsletter	Description and access	# Subscribers	Open rate [# / %]	Click rate [# / %]
#1 – Sep 2017	Introduction of the LandSense project and the LandSense Themes (Link)	159	79 / 49.7%	27 / 17.0%
#2 – Dec 2017	Reporting back on the LandSense 1-year workshop and other relevant news. Informing about upcoming events in 2018 (Link)	188	92 / 48.9%	26 / 13.8%
Special edition – Feb 2018	Informing about the LandSense Innovation Challenge and the application process (Link)	193	81/42%	18/9,3%

4.1.5 Blog of partners and researchers in the project

Blogs are an important tool to communicate research developments, institutional activities and results to a wider public. In addition, they serve as a platform to raise awareness of published articles, events, LandSense Campaigns, etc. Several LandSense consortium partners are active bloggers and they are using their personal or institutional blogs in order to highlight and discuss LandSense activities, results and events (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Example of news entry on the GeoVille homepage

Further, LandSense has been featured as project of the week by the Doing it together science (DITOs) project in in October 2017 (Figure 3).

Figure 3: DITOs blog entry about the LandSense project

4.2 Offline communication

4.2.1 Brochure and promotional material

LandSense has produced several promotional materials: A folder, a template, a brochure and a roll-up/poster. These visuals are used for promoting events such as dedicated stakeholder workshops and conferences as well as to create and enhance awareness of LandSense.

The LandSense brochure includes a brief summary of the project, including a description of the LandSense themes, the LEP as well as a list of the consortium partners and contact information (Figure 4).

Figure 4: The LandSense brochure, designed as a 6 page roll fold pamphlet.

Further, it is envisaged to create a dedicated flyer for each of the LandSense Themes including a brief description of the respective pilot cases. The ensemble of the above listed material will also be part of the Dissemination Kit designed for stakeholders of LandSense and published on the LandSense Engagement Platform.

4.2.2 Scientific Publications

In order to disseminate research findings and outputs, while simultaneously keeping the long-term impact of LandSense in mind, the project will also target key relevant scientific journals. A total of 20 scientific journal articles are planned as a dissemination output for the LandSense project. A special issue in the journal Land (http://www.mdpi.com/journal/land/special_issues/LandSense) will include at least 2 to 3 papers from LandSense, documenting different demo cases.

All research partners of the LandSense consortium will contribute to disseminating the results in Europe, and also globally, via publications in peer-reviewed scientific journals. Because of the broad scope and multidisciplinary nature of the project, publications will deliberately be aimed at different journals in order to access different audiences.

Other scientific dissemination includes presentations or posters at scientific conferences showcasing LandSense research. Posters will follow the LandSense branding rules and guidelines to reference the European Commission's (EC) funding.

Already at this point, LandSense partners have presented the project at various events and a variety of scientific papers have been published as follows:

Herold, Martin; See, Linda; Tsendbazar, Nandika; Fritz, Steffen, 2016: Towards an Integrated Global Land Cover Monitoring and Mapping System. *Remote Sens.*, 8, 1036, doi:10.3390/rs8121036

See, L.; Laso Bayas, J.C.; Schepaschenko, D.; Perger, C.; Dresel, C.; Maus, V.; Salk, C.; Weichselbaum, J.; Lesiv, M.; McCallum, I.; Moorthy, I.; Fritz, S. 2017: LACO-Wiki: A New Online Land Cover Validation Tool Demonstrated Using GlobeLand30 for Kenya. *Remote Sens.*, 9, 754.

Fonte, C.C.; Minghini, M.; Patriarca, J.; Antoniou, V.; See, L.; Skopeliti, A. Generating Up-to-Date and Detailed Land Use and Land Cover Maps Using OpenStreetMap and GlobeLand30. *ISPRS Int. J. Geo-Inf.* 2017, 6, 125.

Fritz, S.; Fonte, C.C.; See, L. The Role of Citizen Science in Earth Observation. *Remote Sens.* 2017, 9, 357.

Fritz S, See L, Perger C, McCallum I, Schill C, Schepaschenko D, Duerauer M, Karner M, Dresel, C, Laso-Bayas, J.C, Lesiv, M, Moorthy, I, Salk, C.F, Danylo, O, Sturn, T, Albrecht, F, You, L, Kraxner, F, Obersteiner, M. 2017. A global dataset of crowdsourced land cover and land use reference data. *Scientific Data* 4: p. 170075. doi:10.1038/sdata.2017.75

Jonietz, D.; Antonio, V.; See, L.; Zipf, A. Highlighting Current Trends in Volunteered Geographic Information. *ISPRS Int. J. Geo-Inf.* 2017, 6, 202.

Schultz, M., Janek Voss, Michael Auer, Sarah Carter, Alexander Zipf, 2017: Open land cover from OpenStreetMap and remote sensing, *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 63, Pages 206-213, ISSN 0303-2434, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2017.07.014>.

All LandSense publications can be further accessed via [OpenAIRE](#).

4.2.3 Deliverables

LandSense deliverables are official project outputs, presenting specific results in relation to the work packages of the project. Some of the LandSense deliverables are public reports and are prominently posted on the LandSense homepage (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Example of a deliverable on the LEP

Depending on the specific content, the deliverables will be of interest to various target groups. In order to make them available, public deliverables will be downloadable from the LandSense project website as well as the LandSense Engagement Platform. Further, dedicated news entries on the website and social media channels will inform the wider public about new LandSense outputs.

4.2.4 Networking, meetings and events

Well-chosen scientific and popular science conferences and events are crucial channels for raising awareness and promoting LandSense activities and outputs. In 2016/17, LandSense partners have taken part in a total of 26 conferences and events, addressing topics such as Citizen Sciences, Earth Observation, Land cover and big data processing.

Table 4 summarizes a series of project related events and workshops that are set to take place until the end of the current (2018) calendar year. This list will be progressively expanded as further events are planned.

Table 4: LandSense internal and external event planning for 2018 (as of February 2018).

Date	Location	Event	Goal	Scope
25.01.	Laxenburg, Austria	LandSense Privacy and Licensing Workshop	Informing about the different license options available for the LandSense Campaigns	Internal
26.02 – 01.03	Spitzingsee, Germany	LandSense WP3 Meeting	Further development and deployment of the LandSense Engagement Platform	Internal
14.03	Berlin, Germany	DFN Betriebstagung	Discuss current and future challenges of establishing a federation system for LandSense	External
03.06.	Geneva, Switzerland	LandSense Innovation Challenge	The LandSense Challenge targets individuals, web- entrepreneurs, start-ups and SMEs coming from all participating Horizon 2020 countries, to present innovative IT solutions addressing one of the three LandSense domains. Full day event with challenge finalists	External
04.06 - 06.06.	Geneva, Switzerland	Second International ECSA Conference	The main topics of the conference include discussing the role that citizen science plays to empower citizens and to increase scientific literacy, the reasons why citizens engage in citizen science, and the impacts of citizen science on social innovations, among many other related topics. Contribution to H2020 CSA WeObserve Communities of Practice	External
12.06- 14.06	Dublin, Ireland	Google Earth Engine User Summit	The summit is designed for remote sensing and GIS specialists who are actively working on projects involving Earth Engine, and for people interested in learning how to use the Earth Engine platform to perform planetary-scale geospatial analyses.	External
23.05	Brussels, Belgium	EU Green Week	Presentation on LandSense and H2020 CSA WeObserve during ECSA's "Making out cities green with citizen science" session. Oral presentation	External
03.07.	Salzburg, Austria	AGIT / GI Forum	The conference provides a platform for dialogue among geospatial minds, creating an informed GeoInformation Society, hoping to contribute to a more just, ethical and sustainable society. Paper submitted	External
1.10- 05.10	Delft, The Netherlands	GEO Delft Conference 2018	The joint Geo Delft 2018 Conference will bring together communities from 4 related international organizations: ISPRS, FIG, UDMS and 3D GeoInfo. There is a specific working group related to spatial information coming from different sources including citizen science. Conference paper to be submitted	External

4.3 Press and media work

Press and media work will include press releases, publishing articles in thematic magazines or the general press as well as interviews. Press releases will be produced as relevant pieces of news on the main LandSense project milestones. Network-related press releases will be elaborated by GeoVille, and translated in turn by partners to local languages, if necessary. If the press releases are related to a specific event, the host partner will be responsible for the local distribution of the press release among national mass media. A press kit (.zip) containing the LandSense project logo in TIFF, a LandSense Brochure along with relevant press contacts is already prepared. The press kit will be available on the LEP as well as internally to each LandSense partner.

4.4 Collaboration with other projects – The EC Common Dissemination Booster

LandSense envisages a close collaboration with other projects and Citizen Observatories across different disciplines, which is explained in detail in D6.1. DEC Strategy, Operative Plan and SOPs.

Under the umbrella of the European Commission's **Common Dissemination Booster (CDB)**, a special relationship has been established with other H2020 citizen observatories, namely GroundTruth 2.0, GROW, and SCENT. A project group has been formed for supporting Europe's leading role in integrating citizen science and building resilient communities that is led by the LandSense Citizen Observatory. The overall aim is to demonstrate the societal and economic benefits of involving citizens in environmental decision making and cooperative planning to enable citizens to become the 'eyes' of the policy makers and to complement existing environmental monitoring systems.

The project group has successfully applied for the Service 2 - Stakeholder mapping, starting in May 2018, as well as the Service 5 - Dissemination Campaign Management (starting Q2/2018):

✓ Service 2 – Stakeholder mapping

The aim of Service 2 is to identify and prioritize LandSense stakeholders and build a solid network to reach them. This will maximize and coordinate the dissemination and communication efforts of the individual projects. Under the guidance of the EC, the project group will identify its main dissemination channels, multipliers and most appropriate networks to foster the level of engagement and the capacity to influence. This includes the definition of a clear methodology and strategy to overcome existing and potential barriers to successful dissemination and communication.

✓ Service 5 – Dissemination Campaign Management

Service 5 concentrates on hands-on support for the successful delivery the dissemination campaigns. As such, the project group will get practical expert feedback on the dissemination activities and will be guided to improve their dissemination skills. Further, the service will provide a dedicated session on legal consultancy to clarify issues related to Intellectual Property and copyrighting. Eventually, the service will lead to the generation of a tailored portfolio dissemination plan, impact analysis, report of initial results and corrective actions leading to joint sustainability beyond the lifetime of the projects.

5 Detailed Communication plan

5.1 Communication Language

Most of LandSense’s communication and dissemination materials and tools will be in English. However, some materials and other communication activities, specifically targeting citizens and local communities, will be published in other languages, e.g. promotional materials concerning the LandSense Campaigns as well as the campaign descriptions will also be available in the country language.

5.2 Communication channels

Some dissemination, communication and engagement channels are directed to one specific target group, while others address all the target groups in general. An overview can be found in the following table.

Table 5: Overview of target group specific communication channels

Target group	Website LEP	Social Media	E-News-letter	Blog	Brochure Flyer	Publication	Deliver-ables	Networking	Press media
Public authorities	x				x		x		x
EU policy makers	x				x		x		x
General public	x	x	x	x	x				x
Business	x	x	x	x	x			x	x
Researcher	x		x			x	x	x	
European Networks & NGOs	x	x	x	x	x			x	x

5.3 Communication plan

Table 6 details the communication plan for the year 2018. The plan provides a framework and a living document, which will be updated and adapted throughout the year.

Table 6: LandSense Communication Plan 2018 (as of February 2018).

Activities	Description of activity	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Website	Maintenance of the LandSense website and the LEP and step by step merging of both into the LandSense Citizen Observatory												
LEP													
Facebook	Strong Facebook presence to reach a variety of stakeholders as well as interested citizens												
Twitter	Strong Twitter presence to reach a variety of stakeholders as well as interested citizens												
e-Newsletter	Development and distribution of the LandSense e-newsletter depending on the relevant information available												
Blog of Partners	Communication of LandSense activities, events and results through partner blogs												
Brochure and Flyers	Distribution of flyers and brochures at key conferences and events												
Scientific publications	Submission of scientific papers												
Deliverables	Communication of submitted and approved deliverables												
Networking & meetings	Attendance at key conferences on Citizen Science and other relevant topics												
Press and media	Communication of important LandSense activities and events through the media												

6 Impact Monitoring and Evaluation

A variety of measures to monitor the impact of the LandSense dissemination tools and the communication strategy will be used. The analysis of actions and tools will further allow us to realign and maximize efforts where most effective, and to revise or abandon paths that consistently do not meet expectations.

For our social media outreach, the TFF, or the followers/following ratio will be implemented for Twitter. We will further use Google Analytics to measure traffic to the website, time spent there and identify popular sections. For further measurements resulting from targeted dissemination activities, dissemination outputs paired with respective measurements are summarized in Table 7.

Table 7: Criteria for dissemination output and current achievements. Note: the criteria are based on the D6.1 DEC Strategy, Operative Plan and SOPs.

Dissemination tool	KPI	Goal	Current
Webpage	Visitors per month	300+	512
Twitter	Followers	2000+	648
Facebook	Likes	2000+	203
E-newsletter	Total audience	1000+	198
Promotional material (online and offline)	People reached	3000+	>3000
Dissemination Events	Number	50+	26
Conference participations	Number	20+	7
Scientific publications	Number	20+	7